

Evaluating Heartbeat Segmentation Methods for the Analysis of Electrocardiogram Data

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Abstract

Electrocardiogram (ECG) data can provide physicians with valuable clinical information related to a patient’s heart health. The analysis of ECG data poses many practical challenges, and the analyst must make several decisions related to data preparation. One important consideration is how to segment raw ECG data – which can include hours of ECG recordings containing thousands of individual heartbeats – into analyzable pieces. Many options exist, but popular methods include looking at time series representations of multiple beats or performing an individual beat-by-beat analysis. Furthermore, there are additional researcher degrees of freedom associated with each approach such as determining the length of the time series or how individual beats should be segmented. This work investigates the performance of several techniques used to process ECG data into individual heartbeats when used to classify arrhythmias. Data is taken from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database and used to train several different types of arrhythmia classifiers. The results are then compared to explore the possibility of developing a general recommendation for an ECG individual beat segmentation procedure.

Key Words: electrocardiogram, classification

1. Introduction

The electrocardiogram (ECG) is a common non-invasive means to gather information about the electrical activity of the heart. As such, data from ECG recordings can be used by clinicians as a tool to assist in assessing patient health. Frequently recorded as a continuous time series as depicted in Figure 1—and sometimes including multiple leads recorded simultaneously from a single patient—ECG recordings can naturally produce large volumes of data. Consequently, there is an incentive to develop automated tools to aid healthcare professionals in leveraging this information to offer clinical decision support.

Figure 1: Example of five consecutive ECG heartbeats from a single patient. (Figure generated using data from [1, 2]).

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With each signal spike and valley reflective of activity in different parts of the cardiac cycle, changes in timing and morphology within the signal can indicate changes in a patient's health. Common ECG features and fiducial points have been assigned by medical professionals the standard labels "P," "Q," "R," "S," and "T" as depicted in Figure 2. Figure 3 provides real examples of a normal beat and an anomalous beat in the form of an RR-interval, meaning from R peak to R peak. While some variation in these PQRST features is considered normal, other variations may be associated with conduction abnormalities. As such, using the ECG time series and/or derived statistical features to automate analyses for patient health monitoring has been a topic of interest for a number of years. This work aims to contribute to this growing body of literature and inform data preparation decisions in future ECG studies.

Figure 2: Example ECG beat with labeled individual features [3].

Figure 3: Example of an RR-interval from a normal (left) and anomalous (right) heartbeat. (Figure generated using data from [1, 2]).

Processing ECG data prior to statistical analysis can involve a variety of steps. In addition to clinically relevant, physiological pathologies, recordings of ECG signals can contain a variety of noise and artifacts such as baseline wander, electrode motion artifacts, and instrumentation noise. The presence of these signal contaminants can necessitate denoising

procedures and the application of filters to produce a cleaner signal [4]. Many authors also elect to normalize the amplitude of the ECG signal in some way prior to analysis [5, 6, 7].

Extracting clinically significant features from the ECG signal can also be an important, and sometimes nontrivial, part of data preparation. Physicians can examine a variety of characteristics related to PQRST features for which normal ranges of values have been established [8]. Many methods exist for identifying these fiducial markers in ECG signals [9, 10, 11], although improvements in this area continue to be an active area of research [12]. Statistics derived using ECG fiducial points can then be used as input to other models for statistical learning [4, 13].

ECG signals, themselves, can also be used as model input in time-series form. In doing so, the waveform can be partitioned to form a data set containing individual “heartbeats” using the locations of the PQRST landmarks, and these single beats can then be used for a variety of analyses such as arrhythmia detection and/or classification [14, 15]. However, there are several possible ways to segment ECG data into individual beats using information from the PQRST features, and, to the authors’ knowledge, comparative results investigating the effect that different beat segmentation methods can have on the results of statistical analyses are currently limited. This project aims to address this gap by evaluating the influence that the method used for defining individual “beats” has on the classification of different clinical beat types with the goal of providing a general recommendation that researchers can use when analyzing ECG data in future studies.

2. Data and Methods

The general approach taken in this work involves preparing the ECG data using several competing approaches for isolating individual beats and then using each data preparation separately to train models for the classification of beat types. The effectiveness of the classifiers trained using data from each beat segmentation method is then compared in order to determine whether the data preparation has an impact on the results. The remainder of this section provides additional information about the data, the beat segmentation methods, and classification procedures used in this project.

2.1 MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database

In our experiments, we use the commonly studied MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [1], available on PhysioNet [2], containing a set of 48 ECG recordings that are each approximately 30 minutes long. Initial processing of the data is carried out according to [15]. Of the original 48 recordings, 44 are utilized in this analysis after removing files that include paced beats. The data is then divided into separate training and test sets, with each set containing the combined data from 22 files, according to the breakdown described in [16].

Each individual heartbeat in the data set has been assigned a physician-labelled annotation categorizing the beat as belonging to one of thirteen different beat types [1, 2]. In the literature, these original thirteen classes are often combined into five categories in accordance with recommendations from the Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation (AAMI) for standards of ECG class labelling [17] in order to facilitate accurate comparisons between different statistical analyses. Several of the beat types are extremely rare so the annotations are combined further into four categories using the AAMI2 standard [18]. A summary of how the original thirteen beat types are combined can be seen in Table 1. The resulting combined AAMI2 response categories are used as the dependent variable in this analysis.

Table 1: Groupings of MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database annotations into the AAMI2 categories.

AAMI2 Category	Original Annotations
N	N, L, R, e, j
V	V, E, F
S	A, a, J, S
Q	f, Q, \

2.2 Beat Segmentation Methods

The ECG data was processed using three separate beat segmentation methods. The first approach defined a beat as the signal between consecutive R peaks, and beats defined this way will be referred to as Single RR beats. This technique has the benefit of being relatively straightforward given the availability of R peak detection algorithms [19, 20], and R peak detection is often a step in data processing [21]. However, beginning and ending a beat at an R peak does not conform to the typical framework used in the medical community to represent a single beat (for example, the typical PQRST ordering shown in Figure 2). Consequently, the second beat segmentation approach utilized in this work more closely matches this standard by beginning each beat with the P wave, followed by the QRS complex, and ending with the T wave. Beats formatted this way will be referred to as QRS beats. This beat preparation method has its own challenges in specifying the amount of the signal to include before and after the QRS complex since the timing of the P and T waves relative to the QRS complex can vary. Previous works typically use some rule of thumb based on having a certain proportion of the beat before and after the QRS complex [22, 23]. In this work, we create QRS beats such that 25% of beat is before the QRS complex as is done in [24]. The final beat segmentation method, dubbed Double RR beat, uses two sequential RR intervals. In our experiments, each QRS complex in the preprocessed data is included so that we use each RR-interval (except the first and last in the series) twice: once as the second RR-interval in a Double RR beat and once as the first RR-interval in the next Double RR beat. This approach can be viewed as a hybrid of the first two methods since it begins and ends beats with R peaks while including the QRS complex in the middle. It must also be noted that the Double RR beats are constructed in a way that results in them containing more of the ECG signal than the other two beat segmentation methods which might have a significant impact on the results. Figure 4 shows examples of heartbeats from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database produced using each of the three beat segmentation methods. In the Single RR beats, the clinical label corresponding to the first (left-most) R-peak is the one assigned to the beat. For the QRS and Double RR beats, the annotation associated with the R peak in the middle of the fully included QRS complex is assigned to the beat.

2.3 Classifiers

Three different classifiers were trained for each of the three beat segmentation methods using the training data in order to predict the beat type: k -nearest neighbors (KNN), a random forest (RF), and a feedforward neural network (FFNN). For KNN, the 10 nearest neighbors were used for classification. The RF was trained with 1000 trees and `max_depth` = 50. The FFNN used the ReLU activation function and a grid search was performed for the number of hidden layers, number of units in each hidden layer, and inclusion of dropout

Figure 4: Examples of heartbeats produced using the three different beat segmentation methods: Single RR (top left), QRS (top right), and Double RR (bottom center). (Figure generated using data from [1, 2]).

layers. Two and three hidden layers were considered with the number of units ranging from 50 to 250 in increments of 50. All models were fit using R version 4.3.3 [25]. Classification performance was measured on the test set using sensitivity (Sens), positive predictive value (PPV), and F1 score.

3. Results and Discussion

To aid interpretation, the results presented here focus on the N and V classes. These beat types are the two most commonly occurring classes in an imbalanced dataset. Therefore, it is reasonable to be relatively more optimistic about the quality of results for classifying these beat types. This allows room for comparisons among the different beat segmentation methods, and a similar classification focus is presented in [15, 16, 18].

Classification metrics calculated based on predictions obtained on the test set for both the N and V classes are shown in Table 2. For beats belonging to the N class, the Double RR data had the largest mean sensitivity, positive predictive value, and F1 score across all three different classifiers. The QRS data consistently performed second best, on average, with Single RR data having the lowest mean values. The highest individual sensitivity of 0.989 was achieved by KNN using the Double RR data, and the lowest overall sensitivity of 0.892 was produced by RF evaluated on the Single RR data. The results are similar for positive predictive value and F1 score with KNN applied to the Double RR data obtaining the highest individual values for those statistics and results from RF on Single RR data always among the lowest in individual performance.

Overall results for the V class beats are similar. Double RR data had the highest sensitivity, positive predictive value, and F1 score averaged over the three classifiers. Single

RR data again had the lowest mean results with the QRS data results falling in the middle. There was, however, some variability in the top and lowest performing individual results. A FFNN using the Double RR data achieved the highest sensitivity of 0.909 while the lowest sensitivity came from KNN applied to the QRS data. For positive predictive value, KNN on the Double RR data obtained the largest value of 0.914 with RF on the Single RR data performed worst at 0.386. The highest F1 score of 0.873 came from KNN on the Double RR data, and the lowest value of 0.525 was observed with Single RR data and the RF classifier.

Collectively, these results indicate that the Double RR data preparation should be preferred for the classification of both N and V beats. This is not entirely surprising since an individual Double RR beat contains more of the ECG signal than a Single RR or QRS beat. However, defining an individual beat to contain this much of the signal might not always be desirable, and a researcher might prefer to focus only on methods that limit the amount of data to that which does not contain multiple Q and S waves. Out of the two beat segmentation methods that satisfy this condition, QRS beats clearly performed better than Single RR beats for both classes of beats.

While a comparison of the different data preparations in the main goal of this analysis, it is also possible to more carefully look into any possible differences amongst the classifiers. For instance, in Table 2, a closer look at the individual classification results reveals that FFNN using Single RR beats actually performs better than FFNN using QRS beats in two out of the three metrics for both N and V classes. As such, although we have seen that QRS beats tend to lead to better results than Single RR beats in averaging across the different classifiers, we also acknowledge that different data preparations may be preferred for different classification objectives and should be further investigated in future works.

Table 2: Classification results for classes N and V using the three different beat definitions as input to KNN, RF, and FFNN classifiers. The highest and lowest values for each metric across all data segmentations and classifiers are bolded and italicized, respectively.

	N Class			V Class		
	Sens	PPV	F1	Sens	PPV	F1
Single RR						
KNN	0.915	0.942	0.928	0.818	0.503	0.623
RF	<i>0.892</i>	<i>0.940</i>	<i>0.916</i>	0.820	<i>0.386</i>	<i>0.525</i>
FFNN	0.942	0.944	0.943	0.778	0.590	0.671
QRS						
KNN	0.953	<i>0.940</i>	0.946	<i>0.759</i>	0.644	0.697
RF	0.964	0.948	0.956	0.857	0.675	0.755
FFNN	0.913	0.952	0.933	0.837	0.514	0.637
Double RR						
KNN	0.989	0.988	0.968	0.835	0.914	0.873
RF	0.973	0.947	0.960	0.841	0.723	0.777
FFNN	0.964	0.957	0.960	0.909	0.764	0.830

4. Conclusion

This project compared the effectiveness of three heartbeat segmentation methods for ECG data when classifying individual heartbeat types. In general, the results indicate that there is

a practical difference in the quality of the classification results obtained using the different segmentation methods. The data preparation with heartbeats defined using two consecutive RR intervals produced the best results overall. Heartbeats defined with the QRS complex intact and between the P and T waves were typically second best, on average, and data prepared using beats created from a single RR interval tended to yield the poorest performance. These results can help researchers performing individual-beat analyses using ECG data make more informed decisions about how to process their data in an effort to improve classification performance.

As these results were generated using off-the-shelf classification methods, future studies may build off of this work in looking at more involved, state-of-the-art ECG classification methods. In addition, where we have only looked at the results generated for N and V classes of the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database, it may of interest to see if these classification patterns persist for other data sets and additional class types.

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